

EXPLORATION OF ALUMINIUM CHIPS AND GEL COAT TECHNIQUE FOR TEXTURAL ENHANCEMENT OF FIBRE-GLASS SCULPTURE: A STUDIO REPORT

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ABSTRACT

It has been observed that fibreglass sculptures have been produced by many sculptors, frequently using a particular set of chemical materials such as Resin, Calcium or marble dust combinations. These commonly known materials contribute to the lack of textural quality of the sculpture and most times cannot be exhibited unless they are patinated. Sculptors are also faced with the challenges of extrinsic patination, using manufactured paints; which reduces the aesthetic quality of a good sculpture. This study "Exploration of Aluminium Chips and Gel coat for fibreglass sculpture Production aims at exploring the use of aluminium chips and gel coat to produce fable-top sculptures depicting wildlife. The aim of this study is the production of sculptures using aluminium chips and gel coat: To achieve that, the sculpture studio exploratory environment was adopted, using Practice-Led visual arts research methods. The paper revealed that gel-coat and aluminium chips in addition to the traditional composite fibreglass material can be used as alternate sculpture materials to achieve a successfully finished sculptural piece with a unique texture. Although this is rare; the exploration was successful, it replaces extrinsic patination procedure, which is laborious, time-consuming and expensive. While the gel-coat and aluminium combination is intrinsic and less expensive, aluminium chips which are practically wastes can also be recycled and used as an alternative material for the production of sculpture without an extrinsic patination process.

Keywords: Exploration, Patination, Sculpture and Production.

INTRODUCTION

The origin of the art of sculpture dates back to the origin of man, synchronizing with the primaevial experiences of the pre-historic man. The early man suddenly developed the need to improve upon his skills and similarly to subject the chaotic character of nature to a portable size and gain a certain measure of control and promote fertility. He achieved this by carving out or making incised contours of the figure of animals on the walls of the caves and stones with sticks and fingers. As man's scope and experiences widened, there came into being the need for man to experiment with different materials like alabaster and limestone, for a few to mention. According to Barton (2002:29) life-size and even larger statues, carved in slate, alabaster, and limestone, were as regular and simple in shape as the tombs themselves. Artists, both contemporary and traditional confirm the notion that there exists a relationship between them and their environment. Moffat (2007) opines that "the cave art of all social groups consists of five principal motifs: human figures, animals, tools and weapons, rudimentary local maps and symbols or ideograms". To further buttress this, Adams (2007) says the upper Palaeolithic man produced a wide range of small sculptures made from Ivory, bone, clay and stone. These depict humans, animals and a combination of the two". In today's world of sculpture production, there are many media and techniques for sculpture production such as wood carving, metal construction, casting, and direct cement modelling and so on.

Over the years, different artists have used different media to express their creativity in sculpture, while some artists find direct cement modelling most suitable; some prefer metal, while some use wood. Different sculptures are usually identified by the medium that the sculpture is made from, which determines the general working characteristics of the material for purposes of durability and sustainability. However other sculptural media provide sculpture as a means to an end. At the finishing level, the sculptures are patinated often as additional production cost. Also, some sculptors are often faced with the problem of paginating sculptural works as a means of achieving appropriate finished state to the art pieces. This has however been noted to be the reason for the poor finishing of the sculptural process.

Among the visual arts, sculpture exudes greater aesthetic feeling and commands a sense of touch appeal. Among these characteristics, the sense of seeing is very particular to the appearance of the work whether at a closer range or distance, hence, texture plays a vital role in the process of finishing of sculpture with coarse material or media, especially with fibre-glass. It is therefore evident that fibreglass sculptures, with the use of resin, catalyst, and accelerator and calcium contribute to the absence or lack of textural quality; hence, it must be patinated or painted to enhance the aesthetic quality of the sculpture. The search for inherent and applied quality in the material has necessitated the studio exploration of sculpture production with aluminium chips and gel-cost.

For this exploration, gel coat and aluminium chips in conjunction with the traditional fibreglass chemicals were adopted for the production of sculptures, an attempt to expand the frontiers of material culture for sculpture production and

add to the variety of possibilities in media and materials exploration. Nevertheless, using materials like gel-coat and aluminium chips appear uncommon. It is on this premise that the artists are motivated to explore the use of the aforementioned materials. This study proposes to explore aluminium chips and gel coat for the study with the intent to discover inherent aesthetic qualities in aluminium chip and gel coat combination as a patina free finishing.

In the past, fibreglass sculptures have been produced by many sculptors with conventional media of calcium and resin or marble dust and resin. These sculptures lack textural beauty, hence are rarely exhibited due to poor finishing unless they are patinated. Patination is a process of encrusting with colour, intending to simulate visual effects on the sculpture. This has not proffered artists the opportunities to explore available media for innovations to give consumers/clients optimum satisfaction and widen the scope of utilization of different types of materials by the artist. This thus limits creativity and variations in the aesthetics commands of sculpture. Sculptors are known to have explored mostly conventional media; hence they appear less adventurous in the use of new media.

Since resin and calcium composition offers a smooth blend when used in the absence of other textural media except for fibre, their results remain almost the same as always except for the higher ratio of fibre mat to the mixture (which most times are insignificant). This however eliminates the principle of variety in texture especially when the sculptures are not patinated.

There is the possibility that patinated or treated sculpture surface could be susceptible to fungal growth and subsequent dilapidation. Fungal growth on paginated surfaces has resulted in the loss of several sculptures and others are getting dilapidated. Also, the cost of maintenance of a sculpture when patinated is high because, after some years, the sculpture needs to be re-patinated. Therefore there is a remedial need to explore other extraneous materials that would not require patination and yet give very durable aesthetic finishing. Galleries and exhibitions are usually dominated by works produced with these conventional media and this leads to poor patronage by art collectors. To abate these challenges this study is out to experiment on the use of the combination of gel coat and aluminium chips to produce sculptures.

CONCEPTUAL EXPLORATION

The general practice of sculpture production ultimately ends with finishing; the simple understanding of this is the fact that a piece of sculpture must have a pleasing texture for appreciation. Hence, the conventionality is therefore on the threshold of review and needed innovation. Therefore, some ideas are muted here for studio exploration, with certain terms that are herein conceptualized.

Aluminium

Aluminium is a chemical element in the boron group with the symbol Al and atomic number 13. It is a relatively soft, durable, lightweight, ductile and malleable metal with an appearance ranging from silvery grey to dull grey,

depending on the surface roughness. It is non-magnetic and does not easily ignite. Aluminium has about one third the density and stiffness of steel. It is easily machined, cast, drawn and extruded (Polmear 1995). Agency for toxic substance and disease registry ATSDR (2008) also stated that Aluminium is the most abundant metal in the earth's crust and it is widely distributed. It is a very reactive element and it is never found as a free metal in nature. It is found combined with other elements, most commonly with oxygen, silicon and fluorine. These chemical compounds are commonly found in soil, minerals, rocks and clay. So aluminium chips are the small pieces of aluminium that fall in the course of cutting or filling it, this is found to be suitable for use in this studio exploration.

Texture in Sculpture

Every object has its visual effects as well as the tactile; given that an object is seen, perhaps, its visual quality draws or attracts the viewer to touch. Therefore, texture can be explained as the surface quality of an object which is either seen or touched. Omuaru (2002) suggests three basic steps that can be taken to understand the term texture; that, it is the surface quality of any work of art, it would be identified by looking at or touching to feel if it is smooth or rough and lastly, it is either natural or man-made.

The texture is one of the major elements of a work of art, it cuts across all the various type of creative works, whether, it is hand-make or machine. It is phenomenal to human attitude to see and be amazed and feel satisfied, nevertheless, the finishing of some artworks creates an illusion. Hence the project is an implied or simulated texture, this is because, and the surface of the sculpture is multifaceted. On the surface of the sculpture, the aluminium chips are seen but are not felt because of the filling and grinding with a sander and electric grinding machine.

Goal coat

Gel coat is a material used to provide a high-quality finish on the visible surface of fibre-reinforced composite material. The most common gel coats are based on epoxy or unsaturated polyester resin chemical, by this simple configuration, Gel coats are modified resins that are applied to moulds in the liquid state. They are cured to form cross-linked polymers and are subsequently backed with composite polymer matrices, often mixtures of polyester resin and fibreglass or epoxy resin with glass (Wikipedia 20 15:1).

The manufactured component, when sufficiently cured and removed from the mould, presents the gel-coated surface. This is usually pigmented to provide a coloured, glossy surface that improves the aesthetic appearance of the work, such as sculpture made with cultured marble. Many marine craft and aircraft are manufactured using composite materials with an outer layer of gel coat, typically 0.5 mm to 0.8mm (0.02 in to 0.03 in) thick. Therefore, Gel coats are designed to a durable state, providing resistance to ultraviolet degradation and hydrolysis. Specialized gel coats can be used to manufacture the moulds which are turned to manufacture components. These require very high levels of durability to

overcome the mechanical and thermal stresses encountered during the curing and de-moulding processes. Suitable resin chemistries for the manufacture of gel coats vary, but the most commonly encountered are unsaturated polyesters or epoxies. Within each of these categories, the resin chemistries are further subdivided.

In addition to any pigment a gel coat, contains a thymotropic additive, if necessary to assist its tenacity to vertical portions of the mould whilst it cures. The adaptation and infusion of gel coat in this study improves the surface quality of the sculptural piece of this study, hence the works produced will not need patination.

THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

These concepts and literature expressed in the text do not stand by themselves; there are theories of art by academics and philosophers with articulated expositions that mark directions for this paper. It is, therefore, necessary to discuss some of the related theories, for the reason of space, which is Imitation theory. The researchers explored the imitation theory propounded by Plato in the twentieth century, which has wielded huge acceptance, although with few teething criticisms at modern times. According to (Gonzalez. 2010), art is an imitation or representation of nature or reality, in reflection of the theory, the exploration adopted the production of animals on tabletop sculptures. Art being imitation means that like philosophy it reflects reality in its relation to man and his environment and depicts man, his spiritual world and relations between individuals in their interaction with the world. The imitation theory of an otherwise known as formalism states that art is just an imitation of nature.

Hurshouse (1992) opines that Plato's view on art reveals that "art can never truly represent reality for life itself of which art is merely a copy, does not represent reality. In support of Plato's view on art, Cameron (2013) asserts that our world; as we represent it, is an illusion, a collection of mere appearances like reflections in a mirror or shadows on a wall. In consonance with Hursthouse and Cameron's opinion, it is possible to conclude that for Plato, the only true reality is the unchanging world of the forms, created by God and beauty is one of such forms or ideas that manifest in particular beautiful things. Hence, anything we think is beautiful must be an imitation of the original beauty. For instance, if a beautiful girl is a copy of beauty, then an artist who draws the girl will be getting a copy of the copy. The researcher will apply the theory of mimetic and imitation by modelling sculptural work derived from nature such as biomorphic forms etc.

A Brief History of Fibreglass, Aluminium, Gal coat and Exploration in Sculpture

Fibre-glass can probably be traced to as long as the Egyptian XVII dynasty, about 1500 BC. It is a strong lightweight material that is used for many products. However, fibreglass of sufficient fineness and consistency for reinforced plastic was not available commercially until the 1930s when Games Slayter, a researcher with the Owens Glass Company accidentally directed a jet

of compressed air at a stream of molten glass and produced fibres. After Owens Glass joined up with the Corning Company in 1935, the method was adapted by Owens Corning to produce its patented Fibreglass (ATSDR, 2008), according to Merriam Webster Dictionary fibreglass is a lightweight material that is made from the thin thread of glass and that is used in making various produces like sculptures and speed boats. Although it is not as strong and stiff as composite based on carbon fibre, it is less brittle and its raw materials are much cheaper, Its bulk strength and weight are also better than many metals. Fibreglass is found to be suitable for light sculpture, hence its adaptability.

Studio Exploration with Sculpture Materials (Fibreglass; resin, accelerator, catalyst) and Gel-Coat and Aluminium Chips

Duchamp (1950) argues that creativity develops from exploring, experimenting and believe that the artist should better understand the possibilities inherent in the material if he sees how human hands shape them. Oldenburg (1976) concurred that one can transform everyday objects into art, hence, the sculpture is present in real space it creates a duplicate of reality that shares the space we physically inhabit. Moore (1976), Postulates that the art of sculpture creates a solid object that takes up real space, he went further to state that “Sculpture has real mass-that is to say, solid forms and 3-dimensional shapes that have weight and project themselves into space. The sculpture also shapes the space itself. The empty spaces between the masses create voids that are an essential part of the experience of sculpture”.

All objects take up space, for example, a human being is a living breathing form moving through space. Shapes and forms are defined by the space around and within them. Objects, therefore, depend on space for their existence. Anatsui (1987) emphatical on the need for the artist to understand how to strike a balance between material, idea and the environment as an integrated whole when he states that:

The image, being the eventual evidence of the working of the mind and sensibilities of the artists, is a total visual statement. It inevitably reflects what bugs the artist at a particular time, specific place and in a definite medium. Depending on how sensitive the artist is to these, his statement can be meaningful, authentic, relevant or otherwise.

Gabo (1916) agrees that the strength of an object is not to be identified with its massiveness, therefore in recent time, the creation of sculptures for more practical functionality involves a performance by the people. The advent of scientific methods and discoveries had led to an industrial society, which brought a trend of the use of synthetic materials as well as a search for the new order and social commentary. Janson (1973) declares that painters and sculptors were affected by the adverse effect of modern-day machines, which may have brought complexity which led to world chaos. Inappropriate response to such disorder,

the artists may often have to weld an array of factors to satisfy their personal and public desires. This may involve creating not so aesthetically pleasing works out, but works that are metaphoric and philosophical.

Every medium has its special qualities, whether for a feeling of warmth from the colours from painting, or a look of smooth perfection in the façade of the building or texture of the sculpture. Oppenheim (1936) agrees that the soft fur may appeal to the sense of touch, when referring to his work “object” and went further to say, however, “when holding a liquid, it would feel disgusting in the mouth”. Hence, the irrational combination of the two could introduce the contradictory sensation and as such heightens awareness. Nevertheless, for aesthetic purposes, the fur-line teacup reconstructs a dream where the impossible juxtapositions can happen.

According to Brown (2006), some sculptors, contrary to their predecessors of little more than a century ago, clearly do not feel bound-either by academic formulas or by the weight of cultural tradition - to a common mode of representation. Arleo (2004) insists that “sometimes a work of art is more deeply into us when it has no specific features and so resonate as an archetype”. It is not enough to only render the shape, size and position in space. One must also think of its intrinsic nature, its purpose, meaning, and how it feels to touch, knowing the texture, temperature, depth, and opacity. As a common feature, the medium brings intimacy. Many natural media are manageable because there is a sort of natural economy in doing things and seeing the result in a few days or within a few minutes, while the instinct is still driving the artist to work. It is this instinctive drive that has led to this exploration with new media.

Stages of Studio Exploration (Sculpture Production) Sketches

Various animal forms were taken for the exploration; sketches were carried out both from nature and photographs. One of the sketches includes the head of an Eagle.

Plate 1:	Photograph of a sketch of an Eagle by Mr Ikpo (the artists)
Plate:	Photograph of a Sketch of Eagle
Artist:	Mr Goodluck Ikpo
Photograph:	Mr Goodluck Ikpo
Size:	7 x 5
Year:	2017

Preparation of Armature

The armature was constructed using materials like $\frac{1}{4}$ rods, chicken mesh, butterflies and pieces of wood to hold the clay firm during modelling. Armature in sculpture is a framework around which a sculpture is built.

Plate II

Title: Photograph of the Artist making Armature

Photo: Eteno

Size: 7 x 5

Year: 2017

Modelling

The modelling technique was carried out with the use of clay and mould was taken by the use of plaster of Paris popularly known as P.O.P, cement and silicon. The moulds were finally charged with the appropriate mixture of aluminium chips and gel coat to create an improved aesthetic appearance of granite other than the traditional patination.

Plate III
Title: Modeling with Clay
Photo: Eteno
Size: 7 x 5
Year: 2017

After the application of the cement, it was allowed to set for three days, and then the researcher removed it from the mould for the charger.

Plate IV

Title: Artist Separating Parts of Mould for Clay Sculpture
Photo: Eteno
Size: 7 x 5
Year: 2017

Below is the completed sculpture, using fibreglass and aluminium chips for finishing

Artist: Ikpo, Goodluck Chigozie
Title: The Eagle (made with Aluminium Chips and gel-coat)
Medium: Cold Aluminium
Size: 25xm x 54cm
Year: 2017

DISCUSSION

The general purview of the art world on a work of art is for possession through production or collection. Therefore, every artist who produces one does so to appeal to collectors' aesthetic sensibilities for possession through the collection. Based on this understanding and the desire to create an improved textural quality of fibre-glass sculpture, the exploration was conducted in the sculpture studio, using additive and casting technique, fibre-glass material and Aluminium chips and gel-cost to intrinsically enhance the said chemical which is devoid of aesthetic appeal.

The studio exploratory process which was conceived through creative insight was made manifest through the manipulation of technique, and materials, a simple illustration that gave insight to the processes, which began with a collection of data through various literature, photographs of animals from the zoo and forests for decision making. The sketches were diligently converted to clay sculptures, with resin, catalyst, accelerator, aluminium chips and gel-coat. The study explored the possibilities of infusing aluminium chips into gel-coat for the production of table-top sculptures which recorded huge success, having overcome some challenges; among which are selecting, identifying and infusing the metal pieces into the chemical component. Nevertheless, the challenges were overcome by immersion and made possible through the exploratory and experimental studio-led method. This has led to the production of sculptures, as Arleo (2004) puts it what influences us to appreciate is that which “resonates as an archetype”. Hence, the opinion of Brown (2006) plays out; truly, the independence the artists enjoyed today has necessitated multiple creativity and innovations.

CONCLUSION

The need to widen the scope of sculpture materials has been advocated and advanced for want of creative development and innovation, hence, the studio exploration of aluminium with gel-coat and fibreglass composite chemicals is apt. The findings revealed that the studio experiment was successful; aluminium chips are practically waste, therefore can be recycled and used as an alternate material to create inherent aesthetics and enhance visual effects. Through this study, new media (aluminium chips, gel-coat and fibre-glass composite chemicals) and the sculptural process are discovered, adapting the additive and casting techniques.

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